

Current Trends in Geopolymer Concrete's Resistance to Chloride Ion Attack

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ABSTRACT:

One downside of ultra-high-performance concrete is that it requires a large amount of cement. To address this, efforts are being made to replace some of the cement with alternative materials, including industrial waste products. Geopolymer concrete is an innovative environmentally-friendly construction medium, and the transportation of chloride ions is a crucial component that influences its durability. This article provides an impression of the chloride ion transport mechanism in geopolymer concrete. It summarizes the characteristics and limitations of test methods used to measure the resistance to chloride ion permeability in geopolymer concrete. Additionally, it discusses the factors that influence the resistance to chloride ion permeability in geopolymer concrete and compares its chloride ion transport mechanism with that of ordinary concrete. The article suggests that additional research is required to examine the chloride ion transport model of geopolymer concrete under specific conditions, such as high temperature and freeze-thaw cycles. It also highlights the need to investigate the influence of alkali content and water glass modulus on the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration, as well as the accuracy of chloride ion boundary concentration.

Keywords: geopolymers concrete, chloride ion, penetration performance, transmission mechanism, experimental technique, affect factor.

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INTRODUCTION

Recently, the construction sector has placed a growing emphasis on sustainability, motivated by the pressing necessity to decrease carbon emissions and address environmental consequences. Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) has been widely used in global infrastructure building for its plentiful raw ingredients and robust mechanical qualities [1]. Advanced technologies such as AI [2], BMS [3], digital twin [4], and 3D are utilized for the management and assessment of building materials. Nevertheless, the manufacturing of OPC is a substantial generator of CO₂ emissions, which in turn contributes to the phenomenon of global warming and other environmental concerns including acidification and eutrophication. The pursuit of more environmentally friendly construction materials has gained momentum in response to these difficulties. Geopolymer concrete, initially proposed by Professor Davidovits in 1978, is a highly promising alternative [5]. This novel substance is derived from naturally occurring aluminosilicate minerals and waste materials from industries. It is activated using a high-alkaline solution to form a strong, environmentally friendly binder with low carbon emissions. The manufacture of geopolymer concrete emits approximately one-sixth of the CO₂ compared to typical silicate cement, making it an appealing choice for decreasing carbon emissions in building. Geopolymer concrete is becoming increasingly important in the future of environmentally friendly construction as the global demand for sustainable building materials increases [6].

Current studies have placed a growing emphasis on the long-lasting nature of concrete structures, specifically examining the detrimental impact of steel corrosion, which significantly influences their lifespan [7]. The main causes of steel corrosion are carbonation and ion corrosion, with chloride ions being the most corrosive agents [8]. The ions infiltrate the concrete's protective layer, accessing the steel reinforcement and undermining its passive film, resulting in corrosion. The pace at which ions are transmitted, penetrate, and concentrate within this protective layer is a critical factor in determining the durability and lifespan of the structure [9]. The investigation of chloride ion permeability in geopolymer concrete has become highly significant in this particular setting. Geopolymer concrete, a sustainable substitute for conventional silicate concrete, has great promise in improving the longevity of reinforced concrete structures. Gaining insight into the processes by which chloride ions infiltrate geopolymer concrete is crucial for enhancing its ability to withstand steel corrosion, therefore prolonging the lifespan of concrete structures.

While geopolymer materials have been extensively researched [10], particularly in areas such as raw material composition, preparation processes, reaction mechanisms, and the microscopic formation of minerals, there remains a significant gap in the literature regarding a comprehensive and systematic assessment of their resistance to chloride ion permeability [11-12]. Although recent studies have made strides in exploring the anti-chloride ion permeability of geopolymer concrete, the findings are scattered, and a coherent summary is still lacking. Below are the main highlights:

- Significant progress has been achieved in comprehending the resistance of geopolymer concrete to the permeation of chloride ions.
- Despite advancements, there remains a dearth of a thorough and methodical assessment on the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration.
- The objective of this study is to consolidate the knowledge on the mechanisms of chloride ion transport in geopolymer concrete.
- This study will investigate testing methodologies and the primary parameters that impact the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration.

MECHANISM OF CHLORIDE ION TRANSPORT

Basic Model

The main modes of chloride ion transport in geopolymer concrete include diffusion, electromigration, thermal migration, and convection. Diffusion is the process by which ions flow from high concentration regions to low concentration regions driven by chemical potential gradients. Diffusion can be divided into steady-state diffusion and non-steady state diffusion. When diffusion is in steady state, the expression for diffusion flux [13-14] is as:

$$J_i = -D_i \frac{dC}{dx} \quad (1)$$

here, J_i represented the diffusion flux, $mol/(m^2s)$; D_i is the diffusion coefficient, m^2/s ; C is the concentration of chloride ions, mol/m^3 ; x is the positional variable, m. The transport of chloride ions in practical engineering is mostly non steady state diffusion, and its diffusion flux will change over time. The expression for non steady state diffusion is as:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

where, D is the non-steady state diffusion coefficient of chloride ions, m^2/s ; and T is the migration time, s. Electromigration refers to the movement of charged ions from low potential to high potential under the influence of electric field force. Figure 1 shows the migration process of accelerated chloride ion migration test.

Figure 1. Migration Process of Accelerated Chloride Ion Migration Test
Source: [15]

When the applied voltage is high, the specimen will generate a large amount of heat, and the metal will dissolve in the positive electrode chamber and oxidize in the negative electrode chamber. The expression for the electrical migration flux of chloride ions under the action of an electric field is shown in equation (3).

$$J_N = -D_i C \frac{\lambda F \nabla \Psi}{RT_a} \quad (3)$$

where, J_N is the electric migration flux, $mol/(m^2s)$. λ is the number of charges of a charged ion. The F is Faraday's constant and R is the molar gas constant. T_a is the absolute temperature, K; Ψ is the potential, V.

Updated Model

Due to the combined effects of multiple factors on chloride ion permeation in concrete structures during actual service environments, the modified models for chloride ion transport in geopolymer concrete established by existing research mainly involve analysis under multi factor coupling. When the aluminum content in fly ash concrete is high, it will change the gel structure of concrete, thus inhibiting the transmission of chloride ions. Based on this, Wang et al. [16] considered the influence of compressive stress on electrical flux and corrected the coefficient of α :

$$C_b = \frac{\alpha C_f}{1+4.0C_f} \quad (4)$$

here, $\alpha = \lambda(-15.5b^2 + 1.8b + 11.8)$ ($0 \leq b \leq 0.3, 0.5 \leq \lambda \leq 2$), where, b is the amount of lithium slag substitution and λ is the correction factor. At present, research on the resistance of geopolymers to chloride ion permeability mainly focuses on the micro mechanism level, including the evaluation of chloride ion transport performance of geopolymers under different experimental methods, the study of concrete pore structure under different environmental conditions, and the study of the influence of external admixture types and optimal dosages on the resistance of geopolymers to chloride ion permeability. The study on the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion permeability under the influence of a single factor is of great significance for its practical engineering applications under corresponding mechanisms, such as high temperature, freeze-thaw and other environmental conditions. However, there is currently limited literature data on the study of chloride ion permeability mechanisms and models under such single factors, and further in-depth research is needed.

Factors Affecting the Chloride Ion Penetration Resistance of Geopolymer Concrete

Stimulating Agent

The key elements that affect the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration are primarily the kind and concentration of the activator. The resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration is contingent upon the concentration and nature of the activator. Chindaprasirt et al. [17] discovered that the increase in sodium hydroxide content leads to a notable reduction in the permeability of chloride ions in fly ash geopolymer concrete. This suggests that the level of alkalinizing chemicals directly affects the ability of geopolymers to withstand the entry of chloride ions. The study discovered that the use of sodium hydroxide and water glass as alkalinizing agents enhances the chloride ion diffusion properties of alkali slag concrete. Additionally, it greatly reduces the electrical flux compared to geopolymer concrete alkalinized with water glass. As the concentration of the two alkalinizing agents increases, there will be a notable reduction in the permeability of chloride ions. The resistance of geopolymer concrete activated with sodium hydroxide to chloride ion penetration is higher compared to water glass activated slag geopolymer concrete. This is due to the fact that water glass activated slag geopolymer concrete tends to develop

more initial cracks, which in turn create additional pathways for chloride ions to travel through, ultimately reducing its resistance to chloride ion penetration. By examining the variations in conductivity over time, it was discovered that the conductivity of the pore solution in alkali-activated slag geopolymer concrete, stimulated by water glass, diminishes as the concrete ages. The decrease in solution conductivity is attributed to the increased number of pores and the constrained mobility of ions within these pores. Figure 2 illustrates the variation in conductivity of the pore solution in alkali activated slag geopolymer concrete over time when stimulated by water glass, with M_s representing the modulus of water glass.

Figure 2. The Variation of Conductivity of Pore Solution in Alkali Activated Slag Geopolymer Concrete with Age Induced by Water Glass

It can be seen from Figure 2 that as age increases, the conductivity of the solution drops, leading to a decrease in the overall system conductivity. Although the porosity of water glass activated concrete is higher than that of sodium hydroxide, the influence of both pores on transport is minimal. High concentrations of alkaline activators and suitable types of alkaline activators can promote the leaching of silicon and aluminum elements in geopolymers, resulting in stronger geopolymerization reactions and the production of more chlorides. The internal pores of the matrix are denser, and the resistance to chloride ion penetration is enhanced.

Alkali Concentration and Water Glass Modulus

The permeability of geopolymer materials is influenced by the alkali concentration and water glass modulus when water glass is employed as an activator. According to Ma et al. [18], the diffusion coefficient of chloride ions in geopolymer concrete reduces as the alkali concentration increases. Figure 3 demonstrates the impact of alkali content on the non-steady state diffusion coefficient of alkali-activated slag concrete. As the alkali concentration increases, the degree of hydration of slag likewise increases, leading to the formation of more hydration products. The hydration products react with free chloride ions or sodium ions to decrease the porosity of geopolymer concrete, resulting in a reduction of its non-steady state coefficient.

Figure 3. Impact of Alkali Content on the Fluctuating Diffusion Coefficient of Alkali Activated Slag Concrete

As the modulus of water glass increases, the strength of geopolymer concrete exhibits an initial increase followed by a subsequent fall. By conducting microscopic mechanism analysis, it has been observed that while the alkali concentration is constant, silicon ions present in water glass undergo a reaction with calcium ions, resulting in the formation of hydrated calcium silicate. Simultaneously, chloride ions and silicon ions in geopolymer concrete will gather in close proximity to the produced calcium silicate to undergo additional polymerization reactions, resulting in a more compact network structure and enhancing the geopolymer system's resistance to chloride ion penetration. Experimental research has revealed that maintaining a constant alkali dose while increasing the modulus of water glass can improve the alkali activation effect, resulting in a reduction in the permeability of chloride ions in the system. Figure 4 demonstrates the impact of water glass modulus (M_s) on the unsteady diffusion coefficient (D_{nssd}) of geopolymer concrete. At a water glass modulus of 1.5, the unsteady diffusion coefficient reaches its minimum value.

Figure 4. The Influence of Water Glass Modulus on the Unsteady Diffusion Coefficient of Geopolymer Concrete

When the alkali activator is water glass, the electrical flux of geopolymer concrete increases with the increase of alkali content. This is because an increase in alkali content will lead to an increase in the content of metal ions inside the geopolymer, and there may be errors in the results obtained by using the electric flux method to measure the chloride ion content in the pores.

Types of Admixtures

According to the quantity of external additives, admixtures are divided into single and compound admixtures. Bernal et al. [19] found through experimental comparison that when the molar ratio of alkalinizing agent to precursor is 3.6, the chloride ion diffusion coefficient of alkali slag geopolymer concrete with 20% (molar fraction) metakaolin (MK) added alone is the lowest. Conducted research on the synergistic utilization of nanoclay (NC) and nanotitanium (NT) in geopolymers. Discovered that fly ash geopolymer concrete containing 1% (by mass) NC and 1.25% (by mass) NT exhibited enhanced resistance to the penetration of chloride ions. The reduction in the breadth of the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) between the slurry and aggregate, caused by the reaction of nanomaterials with volcanic ash, leads to an increase in the microstructure density of geopolymers. It was discovered that incorporating just polypropylene fibre (PPF) into FAGPC can reduce the drying shrinkage of geopolymer concrete and enhance its ability to resist the infiltration of chloride ions. The study determined that the most effective method of preventing chloride ion penetration in granulated blast furnace slag concrete (GGBS) was by adding 20% (mass fraction) of fine biomass silica (MBS) on its own. The study discovered that the addition of 1.0% (volume fraction) of waste rubber fibres to geopolymer resulted in improved resistance to chloride ion penetration in rubber geopolymer concrete (RGPC). This was further enhanced by the inclusion of 5% (mass fraction) of steel fibres and 1% (mass fraction) of silica. Babu et al. [20] discovered that the most favourable ratio for chloride ion penetration resistance in mixed geopolymers was 50:30:20, with a ratio of mass (fly ash): mass (ground granulated blast furnace slag): mass (metakaolin).

The study discovered that incorporating 1.75% (volume fraction) steel fibres and 0.25% (volume fraction) polypropylene fibres into high-performance geopolymer concrete, which was made from finely ground blast furnace slag and silica fume, led to the least amount of chloride ion permeability. Substituted fly ash with zeolite and bentonite as additives in geopolymer concrete. The findings demonstrated that the inclusion of zeolite improved the geopolymerization process by creating a robust zeolite framework, whereas bentonite contributed to filling voids and increasing the density of the geopolymer structure. Proposed research shows the optimal dosage of geopolymer concrete admixtures, and the anti-chloride ion penetration performance of the concrete in the table is better than that of OPC concrete.

For porous media materials such as concrete, the permeation of chloride ions is essentially the transport of ions in the pore solution. As long as there is a concentration difference outside, ions will inevitably penetrate from the outside of the material to the inside, thereby affecting its structural properties. Research [21] found that adding active mineral materials such as slag and fly ash to concrete can effectively improve its resistance to chloride ion penetration. Geopolymer concrete is generally superior to ordinary OPC concrete in chloride ion penetration resistance, because the addition of appropriate admixtures is equivalent to adding silica rich calcium precursor to the geopolymer system, which produces more geopolymer (N - A - S - H) gel and promotes the stable coexistence of hydrated calcium silicate (C - S - H) gel and geopolymer gel, which refines the pore grid, thus improving the microstructure density of geopolymer concrete, and finally improving its chloride ion penetration resistance. In addition, the fineness of kaolin and nanomaterials helps to improve the compactness of the microstructure of concrete, reduce the porosity of geopolymer concrete, and thus enhance its resistance to chloride ion penetration. When fibers are added to geopolymer concrete, they generate bridging effects through cracks to suppress and reduce crack propagation, effectively reducing the penetration of chloride ions.

CONCLUSION

The research on the durability and practical engineering application of geopolymer concrete's resistance to chloride ion permeability is of great significance. Based on the introduction of the chloride ion transport mechanism of geopolymer concrete, this article summarizes the testing

methods and influencing factors of geopolymer concrete's resistance to chloride ion permeability. The rapid chloride ion migration coefficient method is a widely used and relatively accurate test method for the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration. The factors that affect the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration include the type of activator, alkali content, water glass modulus, and type of admixture. High concentration alkali activators, suitable alkali activators, and types of admixtures can enhance geological polymerization reactions and improve the chloride ion penetration resistance of geopolymer concrete. Due to the late start of research on the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration, there are differences in the selection of research methods and environmental conditions among different researchers, resulting in inconsistent research results. In order to better promote the application of geopolymer concrete in practical engineering, further in-depth research and exploration are needed in the following aspects.

- There is limited research on the single factor transport model of the chloride ion penetration resistance of geopolymer concrete under environmental conditions such as high temperature and freeze-thaw cycles, and further in-depth studies are needed.
- The test method for the resistance to chloride ion permeability of geopolymer concrete is not yet perfect. It can be reasonably improved by comparing the electromigration test of chloride ion permeability of ordinary concrete, and further optimizing the test method for chloride ion permeability of geopolymer concrete.
- The influence of alkali content and water glass modulus on the chloride ion penetration resistance of geopolymer concrete is still controversial and requires further in-depth research.

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